

The Malayan black bug *Scotinophara coarctata* (F.) [Hemiptera: Pentatomidae]: a new rice pest in the Philippines

A. T. Barrion, research assistant, and O. Mochida and J. A. Litsinger, entomologists, Entomology Department, IRRI; and N. dela Cruz, extension specialist, Ministry

of Agriculture, Puerto Princesa, Palawan, Philippines

Four species of *Scotinophara* black bugs have been recorded in the Philippines — *S. cinerea* Le Guill. (Hasegawa, 1971) (*S. cinerea* is now synonymous with *S. coarctata*), *S. scotti* Horvath (Miyamoto, Japan, pers. comm.), *S. ochracea*

(Dist.), and *S. lurida* (Burm.) (Wongsiri, 1975) — but none have been reported as rice pests.

In February 1982, a new pest, the Malayan black bug *S. coarctata* (F.) (confirmed by Miyamoto) was found in Bonobono, Batarasa, South Palawan. A major outbreak followed during March-June, and spread toward central and

northern Palawan, covering 4,500 ha. Estimated populations averaged 79-188 adults/m² (>400/m² in one field in Nara) and chemical control cost the provincial government US\$20,000.

The adult bug is 7-9 mm long, has a black head, collar, and cicatrices; yellowish brown antennae; and reddish to dark brown thorax with yellow tinge; pale to dark brown abdomen; and reddish brown legs with yellowish tibiae and tarsi.

A female lays 40-60 eggs and guards them until they hatch. Each egg measures 1 mm long, is greenish when laid, and turns pinkish as it matures. The nymph is brown with yellowish green abdomen and 2-3 black scent glands. Pentatomid species from rice fields in Palawan can be identified using the following key (see figure):

1. Prehumeral spine prominent; body coloration dark brown to black 2
- Prehumeral spine partially developed to entirely absent, body coloration not as above 4
2. Tip of anterolateral spine projected backward; head across eyes nearly twice as wide as long; width across prehumeral process 4-4.5 mm; antennal segment I as long as II and III combined *S. coarctata* (Fabricius) (Fig. A)
- Tip of anterolateral spine projected forward 3
3. Width across prehumeral process 5.5-6.0 mm; head width across eyes about 1/4 wider than long; antennal segment I shorter than II, segments III and IV nearly equal, and segment V about 1/3 longer than IV; tip of anterolateral spine extended beyond anterior angle of pronotum *S. lurida* (Burmeister)
- Width across prehumeral process 5.0 mm; head width across eyes more than 1/3 wider than long; antennal segments I and II nearly equal, segments III and IV nearly equal, segment V = II + III; tip of anterolateral spine not extended beyond anterior angle of pronotum *S. ochracea* (Distant)
4. Body about 2.0-2.5 mm long; body strongly convex and ovoid; broadly rounded scutellum nearly as wide and long as abdomen; proboscis extended up to abdominal segment IV near genus *Seponia* (Fig. B)
- Body 5.3-17 mm long; scutellum shorter and smaller than abdomen; reach of proboscis rarely up to abdominal segment IV 5
5. Abdominal segment III with a long ventral spine-like process pointed forward reaching coxa II 6
- Abdominal segment III without a long ventral process 7
6. Scutellum with black spots, 1 central and a pair each along lateral and basal margins; width across base of scutellum 2.66-3.00 mm, length 2.50-2.90 mm; antennal segment II ≤ III < IV > V; head length 1.33-1.40 mm *Pygomenida bengalensis* (Westwood) (Fig. C)
- Scutellum yellowish brown without black spots; width across base of scutellum 2.00-2.58 mm, length 2.00-2.62 mm; antennal segment II = III < IV ≥ V; head length 1.16-1.33 mm *Pygomenida varipennis* (Westwood) (Fig. D)
7. Body length 12.5-17.0 mm; body uniformly green; scutellum slightly tapering towards apex; reach of proboscis up to coxa III; antennal segment II < III = V < IV *Nezara viridula* (Linnaeus) (Fig. E)
- Body length < 7 mm; body brownish; apically rounded scutellum; proboscis up to abdominal segment IV; legs mottled with brown punctations 8
8. Prehumeral process much wider than abdomen; lateral margins of pronotum concave; last ventral segment (VII) shorter than the combined length of abdominal segments IV-VI *Eysarcoris guttiger* (Thunberg) (Fig. F)
- Prehumeral process nearly as wide as abdomen; lateral margins of pronotum straight; last ventral segment (VII) longer than the combined length of abdominal segments IV-VI *Eysarcoris ventralis* (Westwood) (Fig. G)

Rice-inhabiting bugs collected from Palawan: A = *S. coarctata* (Fabricius); B = nr. *Seponia*; C = *P. bengalensis* (Westwood), dorsal view (C₁) and side view (C₂); D = *P. varipennis* (Westwood); E = *N. viridula* (Linnaeus); F = *E. guttiger* (Thunberg); and G = *E. ventralis* (Westwood).

Barrion, A.T., O. Mochida, J.A. Litsinger, and N. dela Cruz. 1982. The Malayan black bug *Scotinophara coarctata* (F.) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae): a new rice pest in the Philippines. International Rice Research Newsletter 7(6): 6-7.

Seed-feeding rice bugs, taxonomy, *S. lurida*, *S. ochracea*, near *Seponia*, *Eysarcoris*, *Pygomenida*, *Nezara*